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The Relationship between Mobbing Towards Teachers and Psychological Resilience in Educational Institutions

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Abstract

In this study, the relationship between the mobbing experienced by the teachers in the Dulkadiroğlu district of Kahramanmaraş, Turkey, and their psychological resilience was investigated. The sample of this study was formed by a randomly selected group of 290 teachers. Psychological Mobbing Scale (Ocak, 2008) and Psychological Resilience Scale (Işık, 2016) were used in the study, and the data obtained were analyzed using correlation and regression techniques. Findings of the study revealed that there is a negative and significant relationship between the mobbing that teachers are exposed to and their psychological resilience. In addition, it was also found that the mobbing experienced by the teachers is a significant predictor of their psychological resilience.

Keywords: Mobbing, Psychological Resilience, Teacher

Introduction

Effective educational activities can be said to be an important way to adapt to the conditions of the changing and developing world of the 21st century. Law-makers and education administrators should make effort to remove all obstacles against the proper implementation of these activities. Mobbing is thought by researchers to be one of the obstacles to the positive results of educational activities. As considered one of the serious obstacles to employees' commitment to the organization and job satisfaction, mobbing is the harassment committed by a colleague or a group of colleagues, targeting a person in the organization and planning his dismissal from the organization (Duffy and Sperry, 2007). In other words, it refers to hostile behaviours such as psychological terror, threats and humiliation applied to a person or group in the organization by their superiors or colleagues at least once a week for at least six months (Leymann, 1996). Mobbing is a case that every employee may be exposed to, which can have severe personal and organizational consequences. Due to mobbing, organizations can lose their efficient employees, organizational trust perceptions of employees can be damaged and organizations can face punitive sanctions. İlhan Isman, who is the head of Association of Fighting against

Mobbing, indicates that 40 percent of the work population suffer from mobbing and this figure corresponds to 9 million 600 thousand people in Turkey (9 million 600 thousand people suffer from mobbing in Turkey, 2018). Teaching is one of the professions where mobbing is most experienced. Hubert and Veldhoven (2001) state that the rate of mobbing victims among teachers is 37.3% while Cemaloğlu (2007) indicates that 50% of the teachers are mobbed at school. Moreover, Bilgel, Aytaç, and Bayram (2006) address that 55% of employees in the health, education and security sectors experience mobbing. Based on these data, it can be said that the frequency of mobbing is high in educational organizations, which can reduce the efficiency, effectiveness and quality of educational activities.

Educational organizations are one of the institutions that shape the futures of students and therefore societies. In this respect, the cases such as mobbing, which reduce teachers' motivation, job satisfaction and commitment to organization, and cause burnout, should not take place in educational institutions. It is necessary at schools to prevent mobbing towards teachers, to ensure that teachers are least affected by mobbing, and to equip them with the skills to cope with such negativity. Psychological resilience can be said to be one of these skills. In this context, the main purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between the mobbing that teachers are exposed to and their psychological resilience.

Mobbing was defined as behaviours such as harassment, threats and humiliation encountered in organizations, while psychological resilience was defined as the ability to reduce stress and cope with negativities. Mobbing consists of 7 sub-dimensions as affecting the quality of life, preventing social relations, damaging personal reputation, preventing the person from showing oneself, targeting the self, preventing the person from communicating, and interfering with the private life of the person. In addition, psychological resilience consists of 3 sub-dimensions as commitment, control, and challenge.

Mobbing

Mobbing has been ignored and hidden, although it has always been presumed to have existed since the establishment of first labour organizations in history. Mobbing, which is likely to occur in any organization with communication, interaction and hierarchy, is one of the organizational problems to the detriment of the employee, organization and managers. The problem is getting more serious in educational organizations. The future of nations is possible by shaping the minds of their young individuals. Therefore, it is evident that these organizations should be kept away from negativity as much as possible. Teachers' efficiency, productivity and effectiveness in educational activities depend on their motivation. In this respect, it is important for teachers, or rather, each agent of the educational activities, to fulfil their duties with the highest efficiency and motivation. Being exposed to mobbing can be said to be one of the obstacles to this.

Mobbing refers to all behaviours such as maltreatment, threats, violence, and humiliation that are systematically applied to individuals by their superiors, colleagues or subordinates (Tınaz, 2006). It is understood from this definition that mobbing is not always caused by superiors and includes all kinds of hostile behaviour. In addition, in order for bad behaviour to be regarded as mobbing, it should be systematic, occur at least once a week and last for 6 months (Leymann, 1996). Mobbing is the process in which the mobber expects it to result in the superiority over the victim. Despite the all of these, mobbing generally does not include physical violence. There is no general specification for whom mobbing can be applied in organizations and educational institutions. Mobbing can be applied to everyone, but studies suggest that employees who are envied, self-confident, different, qualified, strong and successful are exposed to mobbing (Zapf 1999; Gökçe, 2012; Çelebi & Kaya, 2014). Davenport, Schwartz and Elliott (2008) state that successful employees would probably disturb other employees and managers, which initiates the mobbing process. Indeed, the questioning, thinking, successful teachers are not liked by the mobbers, and are tried to be oppressed by using formal and informal channels. In parallel with this inference, Peker, Inandi, and Gılıç (2018), in their research, cite the finding that teachers are more frequently exposed to mobbing in institutions dominated by an autocratic management style which strives to preserve the strict hierarchical structure of the organization, try to make decisions alone and threaten and harass employees for this. Contrary to this information, Cemaloğlu and Ertürk (2007) stated in their study that when one person's success in the workplace disturbs others, this situation may create a potential reason for the

outbreak of mobbing, although it is not true to associate the process with a single variable or a group of variables.

Some behavioural and mental disorders can be observed in individuals exposed to mobbing such as psychosomatic complaints, post-traumatic stress disorder, obsessions (Zapf, 1999), insomnia, loss of appetite, distress, crying crises, forgetfulness, sensitivity, sudden anger, silence, loss of desire to live, and dissatisfaction with the things they previously loved (Tetik, 2010). The damages of mobbing to organizations can be summarized as a decrease in the existing power of the organization, a negative organizational climate, an unsafe work environment, unwillingness in employees, and a low performance (Şener, 2013). In addition to all these, it should be kept in mind that mobbing can cause a festering sore in the minds of individuals and organizations.

Mobbing has 7 sub-dimensions as affecting the quality of life, preventing social relations, damaging personal reputation, preventing the person from showing oneself, targeting the self, preventing the person from communicating, and interfering with the private life of the person. Mobbing as affecting the quality of life is a sub-dimension involving behaviours such as assigning jobs that negatively affect the self-confidence of the individual, and do not overlap with their abilities (Karcıoğlu & Çelik, 2012), as well as giving tasks that are impossible to perform, and beyond one's capacity. Mobbing as preventing social relations is a sub-dimension that includes behaviours such as not talking to the victim, preventing the victim from talking to friends at work, being deprived of the right to interview (Cemaloğlu, 2007), and being isolated from colleagues. Mobbing as damaging personal reputation includes implications and behaviours such as being ridiculed, being subjected to snark, being exposed to insults and unfair accusations, and being called with humiliating nicknames. Mobbing as preventing the person from showing oneself refers to disregarding the ideas and suggestions of the person, keeping important information about the organization confidential from the victim, threatening them verbally or with gestures. Mobbing as targeting the self is a sub-dimension that includes insignificant physical violence. Mobbing as preventing the person from communicating should be regarded as being constantly interrupted and being criticized. The last sub-dimension which is the mobbing as interfering with the private life of the person includes gossiping and slander on the victim.

As a result, mobbing, which causes irreparable problems for both the organization and the individual, can be prevented by eliminating systemic causes as well as interaction and true communication. Additionally, it is thought that enhancing the psychological resilience of employees and teachers would be useful in minimizing the effect of mobbing. It needs explaining the concept of resilience at this point.

Psychological Resilience

Psychological resilience can be defined as the ability of people to stand strong when facing difficulties. In line with this definition, Ong, Bergeman, Bisconti, and Wallace (2006) stated that resilience is one of the main mechanisms used to develop resistance to stress and negativities. Human is a social being and needs other people to live, but when it comes to emotions, he is alone. It can be said that people have to fight alone with the loss of the most loved, failure to reach the desired, unsuccess and bad luck in social life. Those who can cope with these difficulties are psychologically strong. People with high psychological resilience believe that the work they are dealing with will result in positive results and they can challenge the factors causing stress in daily life. People with low psychological resilience, on the other hand, withdraw into themselves and experience stress, depression and burnout. In this context, resilience is the positive role of personal differences in reactions to stress and difficulties (Fletcher and Sarkar, 2013). In addition, Terzi (2008) argues that resilience is a personality trait that helps to cope with stress. According to these statements, people with high psychological resilience will be able to cope with difficulties, regard these difficulties as opportunities for learning, take control of their lives, adapt easily to unexpected changes and ultimately will be successful. This personal strength will, in turn, bring advantages to the organization. The high psychological resilience of the employees increases the quality of work life and brings balance and synergy to the organization, which is among the organizational benefits (Sezgin, 2012). It can be said that employees with a high level of psychological resilience, when compared to those with low psychological resilience, are more likely to be successful, and thereby, will contribute to the success of their organization.

Psychological resilience has 3 sub-dimensions as commitment, control, and challenge. The “commitment” dimension is a sense of purpose and meaning that occurs through the employee's passive involvement in daily events without being excluded from the events (Sezgin, 2012). The “control” dimension refers to the employee's self-determination for their life, the ability to neutralize negative external forces and to take responsibility for their emotions and behaviors (Terzi, 2008). The “challenge” dimension is that employees accept change as a part of the flow of life and see change as an opportunity for improvement (Er, 2018). As a result, it can be said that employees who are committed to their work, have control over it, can stay strong and challenge the difficulties in all conditions will be more resilient and successful, thus increasing the resilience and success of the organization.

Relationship between Psychological Resilience and Mobbing in Teachers

Teaching is one of the critical professions that shape the future of nations. It is important to perform this profession in the most effective way. For this, obstacles to the proper practice of the teaching profession must be eliminated. It was found that teachers' organizational commitment (Karakoç, 2016; Durusu, 2019) and motivation decreased (Avcı, 2015) and their burnout levels increased (Tanhan and Çam, 2011) due to mobbing, which is one of these obstacles. In this respect, mobbing should be eliminated completely, if this is not possible, its effects on both the organization and the individual should be minimized. It can be suggested that one of the ways to minimize the effects of mobbing on the individual is to increase the psychological resilience levels of teachers. It can be argued that teachers who are strong and highly resilient and can challenge the factors causing stress in daily life may be less affected by mobbing than other teachers.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to reveal the relationship between the mobbing that teachers suffer from and their psychological resilience. In addition, it was also tried to determine the predictive level of the mobbing on their psychological resilience.

Method

Research Model

The relational survey model was used in this study, in which the relationship between mobbing towards teachers and their psychological resilience was aimed to be revealed. Relational survey model aims to determine whether there is a covariance between two or more variables as well as the degree of change (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). Additionally, the idea that underpins the survey studies is that if people want to learn what people think, it should be asked directly to them (Christensen, Johnson & Turner, 2015).

Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of 2939 teachers working in 210 public schools in Dulkadiroğlu district of Kahramanmaraş, Turkey, during 2019-2020 academic year. The responses of 290 teachers who were selected by random sampling were evaluated. The sample of the study consists of a total of 290 teachers (172 female and 118 male teachers). According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), in line with the sample calculation for the population whose size is definite, the sample of this research is at 95% confidence level and 5% error range.

Data Collection Tool

In this study, two different scales were used to collect data. In addition, the Personal Information Form prepared by the researchers was used to determine the personal characteristics of the teachers. The Psychological Resilience Scale (Işık, 2016) was employed to measure the psychological resilience of teachers. The Psychological Resilience Scale consists of 21 items that express the individual's beliefs about himself and his life, and three sub-dimensions: commitment, control, and challenge. The psychological resilience of the teachers

was determined with a five-point Likert-type scale grading 1 point "totally disagree" to 5 points "totally agree". High scores from the scale indicate a high level of psychological resilience. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for the whole scale is .76 while it is .62 for commitment, .69 for control and .74 for challenge (Işık, 2016). As a result of the reliability analysis made by the researchers for this study, the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for the whole scale was found to be .83, while it was .84, .82, .81 for commitment, control and challenge sub-dimensions respectively.

Psychological Mobbing Scale developed by Ocak (2008) was used to determine the mobbing behaviours experienced by teachers. The scale consists of 39 items and 7 sub-dimensions: affecting the quality of life, preventing social relations, damaging personal reputation, preventing the person from showing oneself, targeting the self, preventing the person from communicating, and interfering with the private life of the person. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for the whole scale was calculated as .82 while it is .91 for affecting the quality of life, .90 for preventing social relations, .87 for damaging personal reputation, .70 for preventing the person from showing oneself, .80 for targeting the self, .80 for preventing the person from communicating, and .79 for interfering with the private life of the person (Ocak, 2008). As a result of the reliability analysis made by the researchers, the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for the whole scale was found .94, and as for sub-dimensions, .83 for affecting the quality of life, .87 for preventing social relations, .89 for damaging personal reputation, .75 for preventing the person from showing oneself, .73 for targeting the self, .81 for preventing the person from communicating, and .77 for interfering with the private life of the person.

Analysis of Data

Correlation analysis was conducted to determine whether there was a significant relationship between each dimension of teachers' exposure to mobbing and their psychological resilience. In addition, the information on whether the psychological resilience of teachers is predicted by the mobbing they experienced was determined using multiple regression analysis. Results were interpreted and discussed in line with these analyzes. 0.05 and 0.01 were used as significance levels in the study.

Findings

Pearson's correlation and regression analyzes were used to determine the relationships between the variables of the study. Findings and descriptive statistics are given in tables.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis Results for the Relationship Between Mobbing Towards Teachers and Psychological Resilience

Mobbing as	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Mean	Sd.
Affecting the quality of life	1										2,00	.793
Preventing social relations	.746**	1									1,74	.730
Damaging personal reputation	.762**	.837**	1								1,64	.630
Preventing the person from showing oneself	.805**	.674**	.657**	1							2,23	.867
Targeting the self	.574**	.737**	.807**	.485**	1						1,45	.568
Preventing the person from communicating	.745**	.748**	.736**	.735**	.562**	1					1,89	.803
Interfering with the private life of the person	.652**	.746**	.798**	.541**	.697**	.634**	1				1,64	.819
Control	-.089	-	-	-.043	-	-.107	-.131*	1			3,81	.397
Commitment	-	.154**	.207**	-	.247**	-	-	.352**	1		4,12	.457
Challenge	.384**	-.375**	-.411**	-.318**	-.371**	-.342**	-.357**	-	-	1	3,77	.399
	-.046	-.074	-.151*	.016	-	-.064	-.075	.445**	.396**			
					.214**							

Table 1 shows correlation analysis results for the relationship between mobbing towards teachers and psychological resilience. Accordingly, there is a significant negative relationship between mobbing as affecting

the quality of life and commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience ($r=-.384$, $p<.01$); however, affecting the quality of life has no significant association with control ($r=-.089$, $p>.05$) and challenge ($r=-.046$, $p>.05$).

Mobbing as preventing social relationships has a significant negative relationship with control ($r=-.154$, $p<.01$) and commitment ($r=-.375$, $p<.01$) sub-dimensions of psychological resilience while it has no significant association with challenge ($r=-.074$, $p>.05$).

Mobbing as damaging personal reputation has a significant negative relationship with all three sub-dimensions of psychological resilience: control ($r=-.207$, $p<.01$), commitment ($r=-.375$, $p<.01$) and challenge ($r=-.151$, $p<.01$).

Mobbing as preventing the person from showing oneself has a significant negative relationship with commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience ($r=-.318$, $p<.01$); whereas, it has no significant association with control ($r=-.043$, $p>.05$) and challenge ($r=-.016$, $p>.05$).

As in damaging personal reputation, mobbing as targeting the self has a significant negative relationship with all three sub-dimensions of psychological resilience: control ($r=-.247$, $p<.01$), commitment ($r=-.371$, $p<.01$) and challenge ($r=-.214$, $p<.01$).

Mobbing as preventing the person from communicating has a significant negative relationship with commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience ($r=-.342$, $p<.01$); however, it has no significant association with control ($r=-.107$, $p>.05$) and challenge ($r=-.064$, $p>.05$).

As a last, mobbing as interfering with the private life of the person has a significant negative relationship with control ($r=-.131$, $p<.01$) and commitment ($r=-.357$, $p<.01$) sub-dimensions of psychological resilience while it has no significant association with challenge ($r=-.075$, $p>.05$).

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Results for Prediction of Mobbing on Psychological Resilience

Psychological Resilience Variable	Commitment				Control			
	B	SE	β	T	B	SE	β	T
Constant	4.294	.067		63.632	3.979	.073		54.842
Affecting the quality of life	-.082	.054	-.164	-1.507	.022	.059	.043	.373
Preventing social relations	-.017	.062	-.031	-.272	.017	.066	.032	.263
Damaging personal reputation	-.094	.085	-.149	-1.110	-.146	.091	-	-1.601
Preventing the person from showing oneself	.005	.044	.011	.111	.055	.048	.120	1.158
Targeting the self	-.086	.066	-.123	-1.295	-.163	.071	-	-2.287
Preventing the person from communicating	-.003	.048	-.005	-.056	-.011	.051	-	-.213
Interfering with the private life of the person	-.013	.045	-.027	-.290	.055	.048	.112	1.132
	R=.438	R ² =.192			R=.280	R ² =.078		
	F ₍₅₎ =9.521	P<.001			F ₍₅₎ =3.415	P<.001		
Psychological Resilience Variable	Challenge							
	B	SH	β	T				
Constant	4.303	.083		51.895				
Affecting the quality of life	-.011	.067	-.019	-.163				
Preventing social relations	.094	.076	.150	1.241				
Damaging personal reputation	-.155	.104	-.214	-1.493				
Preventing the person from showing oneself	.096	.054	.182	1.765				
Targeting the self	-.239	.082	-.297	-2.929				
Preventing the person from communicating	-.032	.058	-.057	-.550				
Interfering with the private life of the person	.077	.055	.139	1.403				
	R=.287	R ² =.082						
	F ₍₅₎ =3.591	P<.001						

Table 2 shows the results of regression analysis on the prediction of mobbing that teachers are exposed to on their psychological resilience. Accordingly, mobbing sub-dimensions are predictive of all psychological resilience sub-dimensions ($p < .01$).

Commitment

Commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience has a significant relationship with all of seven sub-dimensions of mobbing ($R = .438$; $R^2 = .192$; $p < .01$). Mobbing sub-dimensions explain about 19% of the total variance in "commitment" sub-dimension. According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), the relative significance order of the predictor variables on the commitment sub-dimension is as follows: "preventing the person from showing oneself" ($\beta = .011$), "preventing the person from communicating" ($\beta = -.005$), "interfering with the private life of the person" ($\beta = -.027$), "preventing social relations" ($\beta = -.031$), "targeting the self" ($\beta = -.123$), "damaging personal reputation" ($\beta = -.149$) and "affecting the quality of life" ($\beta = -.164$).

Control

Control sub-dimension of psychological resilience has a significant relationship with all of seven sub-dimensions of mobbing ($R = .280$; $R^2 = .078$; $p < .01$). Mobbing sub-dimensions explain about 8% of the total variance in "control" sub-dimension. According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), the relative significance order of the predictor variables on the control sub-dimension follows as "preventing the person from showing oneself" ($\beta = .120$), "interfering with the private life of the person" ($\beta = .112$), "affecting the quality of life" ($\beta = .043$), "preventing social relations" ($\beta = .032$), "preventing the person from communicating" ($\beta = -.022$), "damaging personal reputation" ($\beta = -.230$) and "targeting the self" ($\beta = -.232$).

Challenge

Challenge sub-dimension of psychological resilience has a significant relationship with all of seven sub-dimensions of mobbing ($R = .287$; $R^2 = .082$; $p < .01$). Mobbing sub-dimensions explain 8.2% of the total variance in "challenge" sub-dimension. According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), the relative significance order of the predictor variables on the challenge sub-dimension is as follows: "preventing the person from showing oneself" ($\beta = .182$), "preventing social relations" ($\beta = .150$), "interfering with the private life of the person" ($\beta = .139$), "affecting the quality of life" ($\beta = -.019$), "preventing the person from communicating" ($\beta = -.057$), "damaging personal reputation" ($\beta = -.214$) and "targeting the self" ($\beta = -.297$).

Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

In this study, according to teachers' opinions, the relationship of mobbing experienced by teachers with their psychological resilience was aimed to be examined as well as the predictive level of mobbing on psychological resilience. First of all, considering the relationship between mobbing that teachers are exposed to and psychological resilience, a significant negative relationship was found between mobbing sub-dimensions and psychological resilience sub-dimensions. Therefore, all hostile attitude, implication, harassment, intimidation, coercion and pressure that can be accepted as mobbing negatively affect the psychological resilience of teachers and psychological resilience decreases as mobbing increases; or vice versa, as the psychological resilience of teachers increases, mobbing decreases. In the studies of Ünal and Nenni (2016) and Kayacı (2014), it was concluded that the high level of psychological resilience reduced the possibility of mobbing. Therefore, the violence and continuity of mobbing reduces the psychological resilience of teachers, while those who are psychologically strong are less exposed to mobbing. According to this finding, increasing the psychological resilience of teachers may decrease their possibility of suffering from mobbing.

Mobbing that teachers are exposed to is a significant predictor of their psychological resilience. Mobbing affects all dimensions of psychological resilience. This situation brings to mind that the mobbing that teachers are exposed to strengthens their psychological resilience. It can be interpreted that, although mobbing in educational organizations forces the teachers spiritually in the short term, teachers can continue their lives as psychologically

strong individuals at the end of mobbing in the long term. According to the correlation analysis results, when teachers are exposed to mobbing, their psychological resilience decreases, whereas, the regression analysis results show that mobbing strengthens the psychological resilience of teachers. This situation, which can be seen as a contradiction, is in fact that teachers are mentally and spiritually weakened at the earlier stages of mobbing, however, in the later stages, they become psychologically resilient teachers who can stand unwavering in the face of negativities, tell the truth without hesitation, turn the changing conditions into opportunities for personal development, and take the responsibility for their actions. These findings are consistent with the finding of Ünal and Nenni (2016) that there is a negative relationship between psychological resilience and mobbing. The interpretation made in the same study that the development of psychological resilience factors will decrease the level of exposure to mobbing in the workplace sounds reasonable when considering the results of this study. In her study on academicians, Kayacı (2014) lists the reasons for exposure to mobbing as becoming successful and different stating that this victimization makes them depressed, silent and hopeless. In addition, the interpretation in the same study that mobbing can improve the resilience of employees is also consistent with the findings of this study. In the study of Heugten (2012), it was revealed that those who were exposed to mobbing gained more resilience (flexibility) after the difficult period when compared to their previous life. This finding also supports the findings of the study. After these explanations, discussion and conclusion sections will be included for the sub-dimensions of the variables in the study.

The Relationship of Mobbing Sub-Dimensions with Psychological Resilience Sub-Dimensions and Their Prediction Level on Psychological Resilience

A significant negative correlation was found between mobbing as affecting the quality of life and the commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience. Underestimating teachers by assigning them simple and insignificant tasks, confronting them with difficult tasks that are not legally possible to achieve, criticizing them indigenously, making them exposed to exaggerated inspections and controls restrain teachers from committing themselves to educational activities and engaging in their work. Hoel and Cooper (2000) state that giving very early deadline for a job or giving jobs that are impossible to complete is a common mobbing behaviour style. This situation can be considered as one of the serious obstacles for teachers to properly fulfil their duties.

A significant negative correlation was also found between mobbing sub-dimension as preventing social relations, and control and commitment sub-dimensions of psychological resilience. The hostile attitudes faced by teachers, being ignored and prevented from communicating with their friends, and thus isolated, hinder them from commitment to work as well as making and practising their own decisions in educational activities. As a result, teachers avoid taking initiative and become silent and passive. Hüsrevşahi's (2015) study which revealed a significant relationship between mobbing and teachers' silence supports the findings of the study.

Mobbing as damaging personal reputation was found to have a significant negative correlation with all sub-dimensions of psychological resilience, which is also an important indicator of how closely the two variables of the study are actually related to each other. Teachers whose professional skills are questioned and who are exposed to unfair criticism, snark and mocking begin to be psychologically less resilient. Montalban and Duran (2005) found that mobbing victims are most frequently exposed to criticism and humiliation. These findings are particularly similar to the humiliation phenomenon of this study that occurs in the form of snark and mocking.

A significant negative correlation was also revealed between mobbing as preventing the person from showing oneself and the commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience. Teachers whose opinions are ignored and who are threatened or even scolded tend to be weak in their belongingness and commitment to their jobs. Pranjic, Bilic, Beganlic and Mustajbegovic (2006) found that mobbing victims who face with behaviours such as threat, isolation, and exclusion are unable to work, which is consistent with the findings of this study.

As in damaging personal reputation, a significant negative correlation was also found between mobbing as targeting the self and all sub-dimensions of psychological resilience. Based on these data, it can be stated that trying to prevent teachers from talking with their colleagues and intimidating them influences their psychological resilience negatively. Teachers whose communication with their colleagues is interrupted and who

are led to alienation and exposed to psychological violence are negatively affected by this situation in psychological terms.

A significant negative correlation was found between mobbing as preventing the person from communicating and commitment sub-dimension of psychological resilience. Teachers who are interrupted and whose communication with their colleagues and management are blocked are negatively affected by this situation. In line with these inferences, Kutluca and Sezgin (2007) concluded that faculty members were exposed to mobbing behaviours such as interrupting their words (46%), exclusion (46%) and hiding important information about work (45%).

Lastly, mobbing as interfering with the private life of the person was found to have a significant negative correlation with control and commitment sub-dimensions of psychological resilience. The teachers, about whom unfounded rumours were made, get to become poor in psychological resilience. Montalban and Duran (2005) state that gossiping is one of the common mobbing behaviours.

According to the results of the regression analysis, the mobbing sub-dimensions are significant predictors of the “commitment” dimension of psychological resilience. Accordingly, teachers' taking initiative about their school and students as well as fulfilling their responsibilities are closely related to the mobbing behaviours they are exposed to. Undoubtedly, the most striking of the regression results is the high regression coefficient of mobbing sub-dimensions in “commitment”. Mobbing explains about 20% of variance in this sub-dimension. Teachers' commitment to their work will increase their motivation, and thus, the quality of educational activities. If one can imagine the educational environments in which mobbing can be minimized, it can be claimed by looking only at this data that the current education level would be much better than it is now. In addition, mobbing sub-dimensions are also significant predictors of the “control” dimension of psychological resilience. The ability of teachers to get rid of negative effects and take responsibility for their emotions and behaviours while performing their educational activities, and their ability to direct their students' and their own learning are all relevant to the mobbing they are exposed to. As a last, according to the results of regression analysis, mobbing sub-dimensions are also significant predictors of the “challenge” dimension of psychological resilience. The ability of teachers to adapt to the changing conditions of the time, to accept change as a part of life and to see change as an opportunity for improvement pertains to the mobbing they are exposed to. The finding by Gönlüaçık (2017) that psychological mobbing is a predictor of psychological resilience is consistent with the results of this study. Maidaniuc-Chirilă (2015) found that employees with high resilience show resistance strongly when they encounter bullying behaviours in the workplace.

In conclusion, there is a significant negative relationship between mobbing and psychological resilience according to teachers' opinions. It can be said as a result of this study that teachers who were exposed to mobbing are negatively affected by this situation, even if their resilience and self-confidence are high. Such teachers can experience organizational negativities such as decrease in motivation and productivity, and reluctance to perform educational activities. This situation in educational institutions would damage the educational activities.

As for the suggestions to the practitioners, a clear description of mobbing should be made and all mobbing behaviours should be fairly charged. A team of education supervisors can be given training on this issue and specifically assigned to solve such problems in educational organizations. Teachers should be informed about mobbing and be convinced that no political and bureaucratic power will ignore them. Only in this way can the actual number of mobbing cases in educational organizations be reached. In addition, not the organizational or political position of the mobbing practitioner but what s/he does, why s/he does it and the punishment to be given should be at the forefront as a result of this action. Furthermore, it can be suggested that the mobbing behaviours strengthen the teachers psychologically after certain stages and make them more resilient than they were beforehand. It is necessary to give psychological support to teachers that will keep them strong during the mobbing they are exposed to. Therefore, although not in every school, psychologist teachers may be assigned in the school districts to be determined. Psychologists who can work in parallel with the job description of school

counsellor can help teachers. It should be noted that there is not a single teacher, a single manager or a single student that can be sacrificed in educational activities.

For the researchers, following suggestions can be made. The relationship of mobbing behaviours with other organizational behaviours such as burnout, alienation, organizational cynicism and so on can also be investigated. In addition, the correlation of psychological resilience with leadership styles or change can be studied in further researches.

References

- Avcı, L. (2015). Öğretmenlerin yıldırma (mobing) yaşama düzeyleri ile motivasyon düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi (Düzce ili örneği). Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Yeditepe Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
- Bilgel, N., Aytaç S. & Bayram N. (2006). Bullying in Turkish white collar workers. *Occupational Medicine*, 56(4), 226-231.
- Cemaloğlu, N. (2007a). Öğretmenlerin kaçınılmaz sorunu: Yıldırma. *Bilig*, 42, 111-126.
- Cemaloğlu, N. (2007b). The exposure of primary school teachers to bullying: An analysis of various variables. *Social Behaviour and Personality*, 35(6), 789-802.
- Cemaloğlu, N. & Ertürk A. (2007). Öğretmenlerin maruz kaldıkları yıldırma eylemlerinin cinsiyet yönünden incelenmesi. *Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 5(2), 345-362.
- Christensen, L. B., Johnson, R. B. & Turner, L. A. (2015). *Araştırma Yöntemleri Desen ve Analiz*. (A. Aypay, Çeviri Editörü). Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık.
- Çelebi, N. & Kaya, G. T. (2014). Öğretmenlerin maruz kaldığı mobbing (yıldırma): Nitel bir araştırma. *Eğitim ve İnsani Bilimler Dergisi: Teori ve Uygulama*, 5(9), 43-66.
- Davenport, N., Schwartz, R.D., & Elliott, G.P. (2008). *Mobbing: İşyerinde Duygusal Taciz*. (Çev. Osman Cem Öner toy). İstanbul: Sistem Yayınları.
- Duffy, M., & Sperry, L. (2007). Workplace mobbing: individual and family health consequences. *The Family Journal*, 15(4), 398-404.
- Durusu, H. (2019). Öğretmenlerin yıldırma yaşama, iş yeri arkadaşlık algısı ile örgütsel bağlılık düzeyleri arasındaki ilişki ve bazı değişkenlere göre incelenmesi (Bilecik ili örneği). Doktora Tezi, Gazi Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Er, N. (2018). İlkokul öğretmenlerinde öz yeterliğin yordayıcıları olarak psikolojik dayanıklılık ve proaktif kişilik özellikleri. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Gazi Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Fraenkel, Jack R., & Wallen, Norman E. (2009). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education* (Seventh ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Gökçe, A. T. (2012). Mobbing: İş yerinde yıldırma özel ve resmi ilköğretim okulu öğretmen ve yöneticileri üzerinde yapılan bir araştırma. *Dicle Üniversitesi Ziya Gökalp Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 18(2), 272-286.
- Gönlüaçık, N. (2017). İş yerinde psikolojik yıldırma (mobbing) yordayıcı değişkenler: psikolojik dayanıklılığın etkisi (Ankara ilinde hemşireler üzerine bir araştırma). Yüksek lisans tezi, Başkent Üniversitesi, Ankara.
- Heugten, V. K. (2012). Resilience as an under explored outcome of workplace bullying. *Qualitative Health Research*, 23(3), 291-301.
- Hoel, H. and Cooper, C.L. (2000). Destructive conflict and bullying at work. Manchester School of Management, University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology, UK.
- Hubert, A. & Veldhoven, M. (2001). Risk sectors for undesirable behaviour and mobbing. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 4(10), 415-424.
- Hüsrevşahi, S. (2015). Relationship between organizational mobbing and silence behavior among teachers. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 15(5), 1179-1188.
- Işık, Ş. (2016). Psikolojik dayanıklılık ölçeğinin geliştirilmesi: geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması. *The Journal of Happiness and Well-Being*, 4(2), 165-182.
- Karakoç, B. (2016). Öğretmenlerin okulda karşılaştıkları yıldırma davranışları ile örgütsel bağlılıklarının çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi, Sivas.
- Karcıoğlu, F. & Çelik Ü., H. (2012). Mobbing (yıldırma) ve örgütsel bağlılığa etkisi. *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 26(1), 59-75.
- Kayacı, Ü. (2014). Akademik ortamlarda psikolojik şiddet (mobbing) ve yılmazlık. *Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 12(2), 67-78.
- Kutluca, A. N., Sezgin Nartgün Ş. (2007). Üniversitelerde Mobbing. XVI. Ulusal Eğitim Bilimleri Kongresi Bildiri Kitabı. Tokat, 5-7 Eylül 2007, cilt.3, 691-697.
- Leymann, H. (1996). The content and development of mobbing at work. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 5, 165-184.

- Maidaniuc-Chirilă, T. (2015). The mediation role of resilience on the relationship between workplace bullying and romanian employees' strain. *Revista de Cercetare și Intervenție Socială*, 44(14), 120-133.
- Montalban, F. M. & Duran, M. A. (2005). *Mobbing: A Cultural Approach of Conflict in Work Organizations*. IACM 18th Annual Conference.
- Ocak, S. (2008). Öğretmenlerin duygusal taciz (mobbing)'e ilişkin algıları. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne.
- Ong, A. D., Bergeman, C. S., Biscconti, T. L. & Wallace, K. A. (2006). Psychological resilience, positive emotions, and successful adaptation to stress in later life. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 91(4), 730-749.
- Peker, S., İnandı, Y. & Gılıç, F. (2018). The relationship between leadership styles (autocratic and democratic) of school administrators and the mobbing teachers suffer. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 7(1), 150-164.
- Pranjic, N., Bilic, L. M., Beganlic, A. & Mustajbegovic, J. (2006). Mobbing, stres and work ability index among physicians in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Survey study. *Croat Medical Journal*, 47, 750-758.
- Saunders, M., Lewis P. & Thornhill A. (2009). *Research Methods for Business Students*. Essex: Prentice Hall.
- Sezgin, F. (2012) İlköğretim okulu öğretmenlerinin psikolojik dayanıklılık düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Kastamonu Eğitim Dergisi*, 20(2), 489-502.
- Şener, O. (2013). Genel kamu liselerinde psikolojik yıldırma ve örgütsel bağlılık ilişkisi. *Çankırı Karatekin Üniversitesi Karatekin Edebiyat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 1(1), 47.
- Tanhan, F. & Çam, Z. (2011). The relation between mobbing behaviors teachers in elementary schools are exposed to and their burnout levels. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15(2), 2704-2709.
- Terzi, Ş. (2008). Sosyal destek arasındaki ilişki. *Türk Psikolojik Danışma ve Rehberlik Dergisi*, 3(29), 1-11.
- Tetik, S. (2010). Mobbing kavramı: birey ve örgütler açısından önemi. *KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 12(18), 81-89.
- Tınaz, P. (2006). İşyerinde mobbing (mobbing). *Çalışma ve Toplum Dergisi*, 10(4), 13-28.
- "Türkiye'de 9 milyon 600 bin kişi mobbinge uğruyor." (2018, 24 Ekim). Erişim adresi: <https://t24.com.tr/haber/turkiyede-9-milyon-600-bin-kisi-mobbinge-ugruyor>.
- Ünal, A. & Nenni, F. (2016). Hastane Çalışanlarında Psikolojik Dayanıklılık ve Mobbing İlişkisi. IV. Örgütsel Davranış Kongresinde Sunulan Bildiri, Çukurova Üniversitesi, Adana.
- Yaman, E. (2015). Mobbing and stress. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 1(2), 6-13.
- Zapf, D. (1999). Organisational work group related and personal causes of mobbing/bullying at work. *International Journal of Manpower*, 20(1/2), 70-85.